

Understanding the Default Mode Network's Computational Role in Decision-Making

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Abstract

Understanding the neurobiological mechanisms of decision-making, especially in uncertain environments, remains a challenge in cognitive neuroscience. This study examines the role of the Default Mode Network (DMN) in decision-making, using fMRI data from the Human Connectome Project gambling (HCP) task. We modeled behavior with a reinforcement learning model, the Experience-Weighted Attraction (EWA) model, and a logistic regression model. While the EWA model showed inconsistent performance, the logistic regression model better captured behavioral patterns by predicting choices from past rewards and choices. Analysis of DMN activity during the pre-feedback period revealed its relationship with prior feedback and decisions. These findings suggest that the DMN potentially plays a role in processing past outcomes to inform future behavior. However, the limitations of the HCP gambling task highlight the need for more dynamic paradigms, such as probabilistic reversal learning, to further investigate adaptive decision-making.

Description

Our previous project, done as a part of the Neuromatch Academy's computational neuroscience course, investigated the role of the Default Mode Network (DMN) in risky decision-making, particularly in gambling scenarios. By analyzing fMRI time series data from the Human Connectome Project (HCP), we compared the predictive performance of a generalized linear model (GLM) and a long short-term memory (LSTM) neural network to determine which provided more accurate predictions of gambling outcomes. The study, with the LSTM model performing very well, motivated this current work into how the DMN supports decision-making.

The DMN has been proposed to be involved in the implicit computation of future choices, performing like a reinforcement learning agent, by optimizing actions through value estimates and vicarious trial and error, integrating past experiences and future simulations. (Dohmatob et al., 2020). In the present work, we aim to understand how individuals make decisions based on past feedback and choices in gambling scenarios. We examine whether decision-making can be accurately modeled using historical reward and choice data, while accounting for the role of the DMN network in value estimation. For this purpose, we focus on the curated HCP dataset from NeuroMatch Academy, which includes 339 subjects. The HCP gambling task, a widely used behavioral paradigm, assesses decision-making under uncertainty. Participants guessed whether a hidden number behind a virtual card was greater or less than 5, earning \$1.00 for correct answers and losing \$0.50 for incorrect ones. A neutral outcome occurred if the number 5 was revealed. Trials followed a fixed outcome with predetermined types (reward, loss, neutral), designed to test risk-based decision-making with real-time feedback in a balanced, randomized sequence (Delgado et al., 2000).

We applied a reinforcement learning model called Experience-Weighted Attraction (EWA) to simulate participant behavior and optimize model parameters based on observed choices and feedback (Camerer & Hua Ho, 1999). The model updates the expected values (Q-values) for each action based on past experiences and received feedback, guided by the learning rate (α), sensitivity to expected value differences (β), and the experience weight (φ). The model utilizes a softmax decision rule to simulate choice behavior, where the probability of choosing an action is determined by the relative Q-values of the actions, adjusted by the β parameter. This decision rule is given by the following equation:

$$P(a) = \frac{e^{\beta Q(a)}}{\sum_{a'} e^{\beta Q(a')}}$$

where $P(a)$ is the probability of choosing action a , and $Q(a)$ represents the expected value of action a . The action with the higher Q-value is more likely to be chosen, with randomness introduced based on the temperature parameter β . The Q-values themselves are updated after each trial, with the learning rule governing this update based on the feedback r received from the environment. The update rule for each action is as follows:

$$Q(a) \leftarrow Q(a) + \alpha \cdot (r - Q(a))$$

where α is the learning rate, r is the feedback received for the chosen action, and $Q(a)$ is the current expected value of action a . This equation adjusts the expected value toward the received reward (or penalty) while also maintaining a balance with prior expectations (Rescorla & Wagner, 1972). Additionally, our model incorporates experience weights to account for the influence of previous choices on future behavior. These weights are updated after each trial according to the following equation:

$$w_a \leftarrow (1 - \varphi) \cdot w_a + \varphi \cdot I(a)$$

where w_a is the experience weight for action a , φ controls the degree to which past choices influence future decisions, and $I(a)$ is an indicator function that takes the value of 1 if action a was chosen in the previous trial, and 0 otherwise. This ensures that the experience weight for the chosen action increases over time, reflecting the reinforcement of actions that were selected. To fit the model to participant data, the parameters α , β , and φ were optimized by minimizing the error between the model's predicted choices and the actual observed choices. The error was computed by comparing the predicted choices generated from the updated Q-values, with the actual choices made by participants. A standard optimization algorithm was employed to find the parameter values that best minimize this error.

In this case, the EWA model was ineffective due to a high degree of variability caused by the random initialization of the model parameters, leading to significantly different outcomes with every run. The parameters crucial for the model's behavior should not be overly dependent on their initial values. Furthermore, by simulating the agent's choices and comparing them to those of the real subject, we observed that the similarity between the simulated and actual choices was low (**Figure 1A**). The model struggled to accurately capture the real subject's response patterns, indicating that the reinforcement learning agent was not effectively mimicking the real subject's decision-making behavior.

To overcome the EWA model's limitations, we explored an alternative approach using logistic regression to model the decision-making process. This method (Katahira, 2015) predicts a subject's choice based on their reward and choice history from previous trials. In our model, reward history $r(t)$ is defined such that $r(t) = 1$ for the reward trials, $r(t) = 0.5$ for the

neutral trials, and $r(t) = 0$ for the loss trials. Similarly, the choice history $c(t)$ is defined as $c(t) = 1$ when option 1 is chosen and $c(t) = 0$ when option 2 is chosen.

The regression model predicts choices using the equation

$$h(t) = \sum_{m=1}^{M_r} b_r(m)r(t - m) + \sum_{m=1}^{M_c} b_c(m)c(t - m)$$

where $b_r(m)$ and $b_c(m)$ represent the regression coefficients for reward and choice history, respectively, and M_r and M_c denote the length of history considered for each. This approach optimizes the coefficients using the maximum likelihood method to minimize prediction errors.

This model adopts logistic regression with a logit link function, $P(a(t) = 1) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-h(t))}$

(Katahira, 2015). We chose $M_r = M_c = 3$, as this value represents a practical balance between model complexity and realism. Although increasing these variables could potentially improve the model's ability to capture behavioral patterns, it is unlikely that subjects are influenced by trials as far back as 5 or more. From a practical standpoint, considering the last three trials provide a more realistic approximation of human decision-making processes. This model, although not applicable to all subjects, demonstrates an overall better ability to simulate subject choices compared to the EWA model (**Figure 1B**). As a result, the parameters derived from this logistic regression approach are more suitable for comparison to brain signals. To compare the model coefficients with brain signals, we employed a method inspired by previous works in the field (Daw et al., 2011; Kable & Glimcher, 2007). Specifically, we focused on calculating the brain's average DMN activity during the pre-feedback periods (**Figure 1C**) and regressing these signals against the model's predictors, which were derived from the history of past rewards and choices.

This regression approach allowed us to evaluate the extent to which brain activity during the pre-feedback period was influenced by previous trial outcomes and cognitive processes associated with decision-making. By comparing the coefficients of the regression model, we assessed how well the past rewards and choices could explain the variations in the brain's activity, particularly within the DMN.

Results show that a subset of subjects exhibited a positive correlation, though not necessarily substantial, between their DMN activity and either given feedback (**Figure 1D**) or their choices (**Figure 1E**). This suggests that the DMN likely plays a crucial role in evaluating the outcomes of past decisions and using that feedback to adjust future behavior. This could involve tracking how previous choices led to rewards or punishments and incorporating this information into the decision-making process for future actions.

One limitation of our study is the use of the average DMN signal across the entire network, which may overlook the unique contributions of different DMN regions to decision-making and learning. Future research could examine each region separately to refine our understanding and improve model accuracy.

Another limitation is that the HCP gambling task may not fully engage participants in meaningful decision-making, as shown by repetitive choice patterns (**Figure 1F**). This suggests a lack of motivation to optimize outcomes, hereby limiting the task's utility for studying adaptive decision-making processes. We recommend using probabilistic reversal learning tasks in future studies, as they involve adapting to changing reward contingencies and offer deeper insights into decision-making and learning (Zühlsdorff et al., 2023).

Figure 1.

A, B. The performance of the Experience-Weighted Attraction (EWA) model in simulating subject behavior. The figure illustrates the low similarity between simulated choices by the model and actual choices made by a randomly selected subject, indicating the model's limitations in capturing behavioral patterns. Conversely, the logistic regression model demonstrates a higher degree of similarity to observed choices compared to the EWA model. It is important to note that the first three trials are labeled "No Prediction" (shown in gray) because the model relies on data from the previous three trials ($n-1$, $n-2$, and $n-3$) to generate predictions for trial n , making it unable to predict outcomes for trials 1, 2, and 3.

Additionally, trial types, shown in colors, exactly correspond to the feedback the participant received during the experiment.

C. The plot shows the activity from multiple regions within the DMN, along with the average DMN signal across all parcels. The pre-feedback period includes the timepoints from the onsets up to the beginning of the feedback windows.

D, E. Positive correlations between DMN activity and feedback/choices highlight the potential role of DMN in processing and integrating outcome-related information. Although these correlations are modest and not consistent across all subjects, they suggest individual differences in how the DMN contributes to decision-making processes.

F. An example of a repetitive choice pattern observed in one subject, highlighting a potential limitation of the HCP gambling task for adaptive decision-making studies.

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